

JURISPRUDENCE

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE APPLICATION OF SPECIAL KNOWLEDGE IN CONDUCTING FORENSIC EXPERTISE

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Abstract

The problem we are trying to study in the article is the importance of clarifying the issues that create the need to apply special knowledge related to various fields of science, technology, art and craft to solve the issues that arise in the investigation of criminal cases and the judicial review of civil cases. Although the set of special knowledge is called special knowledge in procedural and criminalistic literature, the main issue here is the essence of forensic examinations that are assigned without the need for special knowledge. Also, the article shows examples by studying the procedural rules of applying special knowledge in conducting forensic examinations in world practice.

Keywords: forensic examination, criminalistic method, special knowledge, procedural rules, type of evidence.

Introduction

In the investigation of criminal cases and in the judicial review of civil cases, questions of an identifying, diagnostic and classifying nature arise, which create the need to apply special knowledge related to various fields of science, technology, art and craft to solve the problem that arises. In procedural and criminalistic literature, the set of such knowledge is called special knowledge. The definition of special knowledge in the criminalistic encyclopedia is as follows: "Special knowledge is professional knowledge and skills in the field of science, technology, art and craft, necessary for solving questions arising in the investigation and judicial review of specific cases" [1, p. 173]. In the investigation process and court proceedings, special knowledge can be used in two forms: procedural and non-procedural. The following types of procedural use of special knowledge are noted in the criminalistic references [2, p. 192; 3, p. 159-162]:

- application of special knowledge by the investigator;
- participation of a specialist in investigative actions;
- examination proceedings.

The following types of non-procedural use are indicated:

- advisory and informational activities of knowledgeable persons;
- inspection and audit activities;
- participation of knowledgeable persons in operational-search measures, including their preliminary examination of material objects and provision of technical assistance to the operational officer. Although the main issue we are trying to study in the article covers the rules of forensic examination

on the use of special knowledge in a procedural form, we would like to express our attitude to the fact that A.M. Zini and N.P. Maylis indicate among these rules the application of the investigator's own special knowledge as one of such forms [2, p. 204].

Main part

First of all, it should be noted that calling the knowledge possessed by the investigator special knowledge can create terminological confusion. Because among the various definitions of special knowledge there is also such a definition that "special knowledge is the knowledge that the investigator and the judge do not have or have relatively little of" [4, p. 14]. Secondly, the mentioned authors themselves call persons possessing special knowledge knowledgeable persons and indicate that "in the administration of justice, these persons perform the function of specialists or experts" [2, p. 64]. In addition, according to the requirement of paragraph 2 of Article 264 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan, "the fact that the investigator, the prosecutor conducting the procedural management of the preliminary investigation, the specialist and other participants in the criminal proceedings have special knowledge does not exempt the criminal prosecution body from the need to appoint an expert in appropriate cases". Here, within the framework of the present study, let us dwell on the idea of using special knowledge in the manner of forensic expertise.

Correctly determining the grounds for the appointment and execution of a forensic expertise is one of the necessary conditions for the formation of the entire system of legal relations related to forensic expertise. Since procedural and special factors play a role in determining the concept of forensic expertise, a

correct understanding of the basis for appointing an expertise involves not only the analysis of legal instructions and instructions, but also the determination of special criteria. In this regard, the need for the following two concepts arises:

- a) the basis for the appointment of expertise;
- b) to distinguish the concepts of motive for the appointment of expertise from each other.

In our opinion, these concepts cannot be considered synonymous. Let us pay attention to each of them separately. In the lexical sense, the word "basis", along with other meanings, also denotes the concept of reason justifying the correctness of any action. Accordingly, determining the grounds for the appointment and execution of expertise, that is, the circumstances that are important for the case, means determining, on the one hand, the emergence of the need to apply special knowledge, and on the other hand, the emergence of a situation that reflects the normative expression of this need [5, p. 280].

A group of criminalistic researchers consider the appointment of an expert examination to be appropriate and necessary in the following cases [6, pp. 61-76]:

1. If questions arise in the case that require the application of knowledge in the field of forensic techniques;
2. If the evidence obtained casts doubt on the veracity of the circumstances of the case or does not confirm them with sufficient certainty.

It should be noted that the formulation of the basis for the appointment of an expert examination as above is quite abstract and cannot create a schematic mechanism of action. The mentioned problem-issue is one of the most important and significant topics in today's investigative and judicial practice. The analysis of the information obtained from the expertise experience of the Forensic Expertise Centers of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Ministry of Justice of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic shows that in some cases, expertise is assigned without any basis or the decision (resolution) on the assignment of expertise asks groundless questions that are not relevant to the case. Examples from the experience of conducted expertise studies:

1. Forensic handwriting expertise: an initial expertise is assigned to determine the executor of a handwritten text, and although a specific executor of the handwritten text is identified as a result of the conducted expertise study, an expertise is assigned to determine whether the handwritten text was executed by other persons or whether it is irrelevant to the case, or to ask questions to the expert regarding the imitation of the handwriting. In the decision on the appointment of the expert, the expert is asked a question about the identification of the specific performer of the handwritten text, and in that decision, regardless of the resolution of this question, questions of a classifying nature may also be asked about the identification of the gender of the performer of the handwritten text regarding the identification of group affiliation.

2. Forensic phonoscopic examination: if the speech sounds in the presented phonogram are heard clearly enough, a question is asked about the word-by-

word identification of the speech sounds in this phonogram.

3. Forensic art examination: the film "Kamasutra" is presented for examination and the expert is asked a question about whether this film is pornographic or erotic in nature. However, the reference on the interpretation of the procedural code indicates that this film is not pornographic in nature [7, p. 258]. The list can be expanded considerably by increasing the number of examples mentioned. The occurrence of the above-mentioned cases leads to an artificial increase in the workload of the expert and an artificial extension of the period of conducting the study, which, as a result, can also lead to an extension of the term of work of the appointing body. How can one assess the presence of grounds for the appointment and conduct of the expertise in such cases?

We believe that, as T.V. Sakhnova noted, it is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of the general legal and special basis for the appointment of an expertise, and the procedural basis for the conduct of the expertise [8, p. 86].

The general legal basis for the appointment of a forensic examination is determined by procedural legislation. Article 264.1 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan states: "Expertise is carried out in order to determine circumstances important for criminal prosecution when special knowledge is required in the field of science, technology, art or craft, as well as in the methodology of relevant research" [9, p. 274]. Or Article 97.1 of the Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan states: "In order to clarify questions requiring special knowledge during the consideration of the case, the court may appoint an expert examination at the request of a person participating in the case or on its own initiative" [10, p. 48].

It should be noted that since the general legal basis specified in the civil procedural legislation expresses a broad concept, there is inaccuracy here. Because special knowledge is applied not to explain any question in the form of forensic expertise, but to obtain information (evidence) that cannot be obtained in any other way. Also, the event that occurred is scientifically explained. The expert does not explain the established fact, he reveals a new fact and gives it a professional, scientific assessment, which constitutes the content of the expert opinion, which is one of the types of evidence in court.

Thus, the general legal basis for the appointment of a forensic examination is the need to apply special knowledge to obtain information of evidentiary value in the case. As can be seen, the concept of the general legal basis for the appointment of a forensic examination is itself quite abstract, and its application requires the authorities or the person appointing or ordering the examination to correctly determine the need to apply special knowledge in proving this or that fact. Therefore, the special basis for the appointment of an examination serves precisely this purpose.

Here, the special basis is individual for each type of expertise, it is a derivative of the general subject of expertise. At the same time, the special basis should reflect the potential objective connection between the

specific subject of research and the legal fact being sought, which logically determines the possible evidentiary value of the expert opinion. To reveal such a connection, it is necessary to refer to the norms of criminal and civil law. It is here that objective signs of the use of special knowledge should be sought. For example, Article 321 of the Criminal Code establishes criminal liability for evading military service without a legal basis for the next military draft or call for mobilization [11, p. 222]. In the investigation of this type of crime, the fact of the existence of a draft, that is, the fact of the subject's presence in the draft, must be determined first. The determination of the summons is based on the verification of the authenticity of the signature on the summons. This means that in the specified norm of criminal law there are facts that must be clarified, which relate to the general and specific subject and authority of forensic handwriting examination, which give grounds to say that there is both a general, legal and special basis for the appointment of forensic handwriting examination. Here, the investigator's suspicion that the signature on the summons was executed by the summoner acts as a special basis. It is also clear that the presence of a general legal basis necessitates the conduct of a special forensic handwriting examination. In a special basis, both the special criteria, which are a derivative of the authority of the calligraphy expertise, and the logical, legal criteria, which take into account the potential evidentiary importance of the forensic calligraphy research for determining the legal fact, form a unity. The selection and isolation of a special feature in a legally significant fact allows us to correctly determine that the need to apply special knowledge has arisen, that is, the appointment of a forensic examination.

It is necessary to distinguish the reason for the appointment of the examination from the basic concepts for the appointment. Here, the reason is not a synonym for the basis, it is more individual. The reason is information about certain factual circumstances that give rise to the conclusion that there is a special basis. For example, in the above example, the reason plays a key role in the information about the summoner's signing of the summons. It should be noted that the reason itself is not the basis for the appointment of an expert examination, the reason is limited to information about any factual circumstances. The basis implies the unity of two criteria: special (the need for certain special knowledge) and logical-legal (potential interaction in cases of legal significance for this case). The basic concept of conducting an expert examination is derived from the concepts of its appointment. Here it is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of factual and procedural grounds. The factual basis for conducting an expert examination essentially coincides with the general legal basis for the appointment of an expert examination, that is, this basis is the need for the application of special knowledge. The procedural basis for the appointment of an expertise is established in Article 22 of the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Forensic Expertise Activities" as "The basis for conducting a forensic expertise is the decision of the person conducting the investigation, investigator,

prosecutor, judge or court decision, or the contract on ordering a forensic expertise" [12, p. 12].

Conclusion

It is important to correctly determine the grounds for the appointment of an expertise, accurately determine the type of expertise and, as a whole, determine the scope of authority in the research conducted by the expert, which is considered one of the necessary conditions for the effective use of special knowledge in proving.

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